

FORMATION OF READING SKILLS IN ENGLISH

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***Abstract:** These two types of reading are closely related and together make up "full reading". In the methodology, when forming the reading skill, it is customary to pay attention to such four components as: correctness, fluency, expressiveness and consciousness.*

***Key words:** reading, civilization, skill, education, analysis, activities, games, methodology.*

At the modern stage of the development of civilization in our society, the question of the formation of the reading skill is still need to focus. There is an overabundance of the amount of available information in various forms, while its quality can rarely meet the needs of society as a whole and an individual in particular. There appears a tendency for thoughtless assimilation of any information that falls into the field of view of a person. In such conditions, the goal of education system - to educate and train spiritually developed citizens who can adapt to the rapid changes in the world around them. To achieve this goal, people need to be able to fully perceive, comprehend and extract information that is contained in all kinds of sources, from articles in daily newspapers to fundamental fiction. Both domestic and foreign psychologists and teachers are studying this

problem. According to studies carried out within the framework of the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and The Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS), modern primary schoolchildren have difficulty in understanding what they read. Educational institutions set the tasks for the development and training of younger students. Following them, the teacher needs to formulate universal educational actions in students. Along with them, the most important result of mastering the main educational program is the formation of the skill of reading texts of different genres and styles.

First of all, it is necessary to distinguish meaningful reading from technical reading, which is considered in the works in the literary reading lessons. Reading is a complex work, which distinguishes the process of transcribing written speech into sound speech and understanding the meaning of the read text. These two types of reading are closely connected and together constitute "full reading". Without mastering the mechanism of reading, understanding the meaning of what has been read is impossible, so technical reading is only the sounding out of the text, while meaningful reading implies primarily the construction of one's own thoughts and understanding on the basis of what has been read. M. Azimova thinks that the mechanism of sense-making is "collision of meanings", when a reader compares different variants of comprehension of reality reflected in a text. K.D. Ushinsky, L.S. Vygotsky and other researchers pointed to this in their works. Today in modern school practice there is often a lot of work on the development of technical reading skills with complete neglect of the formation of reading skills. Although the entire course of literary reading is aimed precisely at comprehension of the meaning of the work. The development of mechanical reading is the first step in mastering the meaningful reading and gradually turns into an action for realization of conscious reading, comprehension of the read, which eventually becomes the

main goal of reading. In the study of reading fiction texts the considered skill is understood as comprehension of the moral thought of the work.

Since in a fiction text it is not the words themselves that matter, but their purpose in the text, the main purpose of meaningful reading of works is the birth of own meanings from the meanings available in the text, due to the presence of the subjective worldview of each individual. Many researchers have recognized the role of reading as important in the spiritual development of a person, but only if reading is aimed at awareness and comprehension of what has been read. Some scholars consider meaningful reading as a kind of perception process, using the concept of "meaningful text perception". N. Ishnazarova states that it obeys the general laws of perception, and therefore singles out two stages in this process. Primary perception of the graphic image of a word and recognition of the formed image, extraction of information from the meaning of the word - which imply the formation of technical reading and reading respectively, the differences of which were discussed earlier. Also, if we talk about meaningful reading as a form of aesthetic perception, the main criterion and sign of reading, according to O. Toshmatov, is the understanding of the author's position, the moral standard of the writer and the subtext . Literature itself needs talented, aesthetically competent readers to develop. The works of the great writers are permeated with care for the reader who can comprehend and perceive the entire wealth of literature. More and more scholars are declaring the particular importance of working on reading skills in literary reading lessons. Nowadays there is a need to instill a love for the book, to teach not just, to memorize, but also to think. It is necessary to inspire each little reader with the joy of thinking, a movement towards a colorful life in the world of imagination. A meaningful perception of texts contributes to the development of

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the reader's personality, his intellectual and spiritual growth, the deepest awareness of the processes taking place around.

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